

ELSI Policy – PENDING APPROVAL

BioData.pt | ELIXIR Portugal

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Part A - General Principles

1. Purpose

This Policy sets out BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL's approach to addressing ethical, legal and societal issues (ELSI) in the context of its Services. It provides a shared framework to guide responsible data sharing, and support alignment with applicable legal and ethical norms.

The purpose of this Policy is to support the process of making scientific data available through BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services in an ethically and legally sound manner by consolidating requirements that are shared across BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Members. It does not impose additional constraints on the use of data contributed to BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services other than those provided by the Data Controller/Provider or existing legal and ethical requirements.

2. Preamble

The BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL founding documents place special emphasis on the development of an "ELSI Policy" to support ethically responsible and legally compliant data sharing across the Portuguese distributed infrastructure. This Policy is established and approved by the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Board.

BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services offer data for secondary use, so our role centres around facilitating secure, lawful, and ethically grounded access to data originating from life science research, clinical studies, and established reference databases. To support responsible data sharing, BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services provide platforms that allow Data Providers to share their data with the wider research community without transferring ownership. While BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL promotes open data sharing, it acknowledges that the use of data may be subject to legal requirements (e.g. data protection, copyright, licensing) and ethical and social norms (e.g. respect for personal autonomy, equity, and cultural sensitivity).

In recognition of the growing importance of addressing legal requirements and ethical and societal expectations in data sharing, BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL has adopted

the term "ELSI Policy" to align with global norms in genomics research and the broader ELIXIR community. The term 'ELSI' better reflects the understanding that responsible data governance relies on the combined consideration of ethical values, legal obligations, and societal impacts. This BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL ELSI Policy serves as a common framework for responsible data sharing and service provision.

Legal considerations are integral to this approach, as they reflect binding norms and obligations that guide data handling across jurisdictions. However, law alone does not always provide answers to evolving challenges in life science research. This Policy therefore recognises that legal, ethical, and social norms often intersect, overlap, or leave grey areas requiring judgment, transparency, and dialogue. It is in this terrain that ELSI serves as a vehicle for reflexive and responsible governance.

Fostering ethically and legally sound handling of data across all BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services is essential to building trust, enabling national and international collaboration, and delivering lasting societal benefit. BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL believes that attention to ELSI considerations should be embedded in the way we work and is part of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL's research culture. It includes foresight, reflexivity, and a commitment to scientific integrity. In this way, the Policy reflects BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL's commitment to integrating ELSI throughout its operations and into its engagement with partners and collaborators. As such, the Policy is to be seen as an instrument for enabling responsible scientific progress. The foundation of the Policy includes specific ethical principles to support its practical application. In this way, the Policy offers guidance on key data categories and emerging areas, including personal data, non-human data, synthetic data, and artificial intelligence (AI), which are supported by ethical and legal considerations.

All BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services should operate within a recognised data governance framework that ensures data—regardless of type or origin—are made available in accordance with legal, ethical, and social considerations. This includes, but is not limited to, compliance with data protection regulations where Personal Data are involved, and the application of appropriate governance measures for other forms of data such as non-human data, synthetic data, and AI-generated outputs.

This Policy provides a shared framework for ethical and legal data stewardship across BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services. While implementation remains the responsibility of individual Node Members and Services, each of which is responsible for applying its principles within their institutional and operational contexts, the Policy articulates common principles and expectations that promote alignment with applicable ethical and legal requirements. As such, it can serve as a point of reference for oversight bodies, ethics committees, and funders seeking assurance that data sharing practices within BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL are conducted according to recognised principles of good governance, accountability, and scientific integrity.

BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services participate in a wide range of national and international research projects, many of which are governed by detailed policies and guidelines that may impose requirements beyond the scope of this Policy. BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Node Members and Services are expected to ensure alignment with these where applicable. Therefore, this Policy is intended to align with widely accepted normative and regulatory instruments in current use for data sharing, but not to replace funder- or project-specific guidance.

The Data Protection Officer (DPO) of BioData.pt is responsible for ensuring the processing of data in compliance with applicable data protection rules (email for contact: dpo@biodata.pt).

The appointed responsible for each of the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Node services is the appointed Data Controller (DC) for the service (check the Node Services page on the BioData.pt site to identify the person in charge of each service).

A Glossary of Terms is provided at the end of this document to support interpretation of key concepts.

3. Scope

This Policy applies to BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services that make data underlying specific regulatory, legal, or ethical requirements available.

The Policy refers solely to BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services as defined by the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL founding documents, i.e. Node-funded Services

provided in the context of Node Collaboration Agreements and on the basis of Service Delivery Plans, and Commissioned Services provided on the basis of Commissioned Services contracts. This Policy applies to all parties involved in the life cycle of such data, including Data Providers, Service Providers, and Data Users, as defined in Section 10 (Glossary of Terms). It does not apply to any other services or research activities provided by the institute(s) constituting or affiliated with the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Node.

The vast majority of data made available for research via BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services is freely available and open for use by the scientific community. For data subject to regulatory, legal, or ethical requirements, this Policy consolidates existing obligations and good practices into a common framework that supports consistent implementation across BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Node Members and Services, in alignment with applicable laws, standards, and ethical principles.

This Policy covers ELSI issues related to the processing of personal data, non-human data, synthetic data, and applications of artificial intelligence (AI). Intellectual property or license considerations are not covered in this Policy.

4. Legal and Ethical Bases for the Policy

1. Legal Basis

As set forth in clause 7, nr2, line f of the ELIXIR Portugal Consortium Contract, the Head of Node is responsible for the implementation, monitorization, control and compliance with the ELSI Policy that is in line with relevant laws and regulations and that considers best practices.

This Policy is designed to be compliant with national laws and relevant international regulations. The BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL ELSI Policy draws on and supports alignment with foundational international and regional legal instruments that represent widely acknowledged sources of legal and ethical principles, principles which are also widely recognised and endorsed by BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Members and the communities they serve. These instruments serve as reference points, providing a high-level understanding of the values and cultural thinking that underpin BioData.pt |

ELIXIR PORTUGAL's approach to responsible data sharing and governance. These instruments include, among others:

- Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 10 December 1948
- Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights, 4 November 1950
- Council of Europe Convention for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data 1981 (Convention 108)
- Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union 2010/C 83/0215
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
- Portuguese Act no. 58/2019 (Lei n.º 58/2019) on the implementation of the GDPR in Portugal
- Nagoya Protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilisation to the Convention on Biological Diversity, 29 October 2010
- European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes, Strasbourg, 18 March 1986
- Regulation (EU) 2024/1624 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts (AI Act)

2. Ethical Principles

The ethical foundation of the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL ELSI Policy is grounded in a set of principles that reflect BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL's commitment to responsible, fair, and socially beneficial science. These principles guide data governance across BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services and Node Members.

1. *Uphold Human Dignity*

Human dignity is the inherent and inalienable worth of every individual. It is not earned, granted, or dependent on any condition or characteristic. Upholding dignity requires treating every person with respect and care, never as a mere means to an end. This principle underpins all others in this Policy.

2. Respect Personal Autonomy

Personal autonomy refers to the right of individuals to govern their own lives, including decisions about the use of their personal data. Respecting personal autonomy means acknowledging individuals as moral agents, capable of making informed choices in accordance with their values, beliefs, and interests.

3. Promote Public Benefit

Research should serve the public interest by contributing to health, knowledge, and societal well-being. BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL supports data use that advances equitable outcomes—whether through biomedical discovery, sustainability, or other public goods. Inclusive participation and fair benefit-sharing are central to this vision. The implementation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles reinforces transparency, accountability, and ethically responsible data stewardship.

4. Foster Scientific Progress

Scientific progress depends on the responsible use and reuse of high-quality data. BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL facilitates this by supporting interoperability, collaborative infrastructure, and innovation across its services. By enabling national and international research, BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL enhances the scale, rigor, and impact of life science discovery.

5. Protect Personal Data

Individuals have a right to privacy and data protection. Personal Data—including health, genetic, and other sensitive information—should be handled in ways that prevent misuse, unauthorised access, and re-identification. BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL promotes a shared commitment across its infrastructure to uphold this standard through appropriate legal, ethical, and technical safeguards.

6. Avoid Discrimination

Protection against discrimination requires equitable treatment and respect for all individuals whose data are used in research. The interests, dignity, and needs of every person should be respected without bias; each individual should be protected from harm and treated with impartiality. Stigmatisation of subsets of the population via certain data analyses is to be avoided even if it may be induced unintentionally.

7. Uphold Scientific Integrity

Scientific integrity requires that research be carried out in a reliable, honest, respectful, and accountable manner. Scientific integrity includes scientific honesty and diligence (professionalism, forthrightness, transparency) in the stewardship of data, samples, and research results. BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL promotes responsible conduct in all phases of the research process—including data generation, analysis, attribution, and reuse. Upholding integrity supports public trust, reproducibility, and high-quality science.

8. Ensure Transparency

Transparency is essential to ethical data governance. It requires openness about the aims, methods, limitations, and frameworks guiding research and data sharing. BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL affirms that stakeholders have a right to understand how decisions are made, how data are handled, and how responsibilities are assigned across the research life cycle.

9. Anticipate Emerging Issues

Ethical responsibility includes foresight and anticipating issues that may arise. BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL promotes proactive assessment of new risks and technologies and evolving legal developments.

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Part B - Specific Applications

The preceding sections have outlined the general principles and ethical foundations underpinning the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL ELSI Policy. The following sections address four specific application areas – Personal Data, Non-Human Data, Synthetic Data, and Artificial Intelligence – each of which presents distinct legal, ethical, and social considerations.

5. Personal Data

The use of Personal Data within BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services should always have a **valid legal basis** and be carried out in a manner that is lawful, fair, and transparent, in accordance with applicable data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Portuguese Act no. 58/2019. Processing should be limited to what is strictly necessary to achieve legitimate scientific or operational objectives, while respecting Data Subjects' reasonable expectations with regards to the Processing of their Personal Data. Individuals whose Personal Data are processed within BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services have the right to clear and transparent information about how their data will be used, in accordance with applicable data protection regulations.

Implementing these expectations may involve practical measures to reduce risks and uphold the rights of Data Subjects. A fundamental strategy for protecting Personal Data is to minimise risks through the application of **anonymisation** or, where full anonymisation is not possible, **pseudonymisation**. Anonymisation techniques aim to ensure that data can no longer be related to an identifiable person and, when successfully applied, remove such data from the scope of data protection regulations. However, true anonymisation can be difficult to achieve, particularly in the case of complex datasets or when combining different sources of data.

Anonymisation should be achieved using state of the art techniques that are used in practice. It is sufficient that the data is de facto anonymised, i.e. individuals cannot be re-identified by the use of reasonable means. When assessing re-identification risks all factors have to be considered, including for example context knowledge that is

available to the data users, access control systems that ensure data is only used for biomedical research purposes in order to reduce available context knowledge, sensitivity of the data, etc.

When anonymisation is not possible, **pseudonymisation** provides an additional layer of protection. Pseudonymised Data remain Personal Data and should continue to be processed in accordance with applicable laws and safeguards. Even when data appear Pseudonymised or otherwise de-identified, it remains important to consider the evolving risks of re-identification, especially as technological capabilities advance. Where appropriate, and in accordance with the principle of transparency, Data Subjects should be informed in clear and simple terms that pseudonymisation reduces but does not completely remove the possibility of being re-identified.

Where data are combined from different sources, or where they are used for purposes beyond those originally foreseen, particular care should be taken to assess whether such **secondary uses** remain consistent with the original legal basis and ethical expectations of the primary use. In some cases, this may require an Ethics Review to ensure that new risks—such as re-identification, or potential harm to Data Subjects—are identified and appropriately mitigated. For example, repurposing health data collected for clinical care to support unrelated research without Data Subjects' awareness may require additional ethical scrutiny and data protection measures. This is especially important when the new use raises ethical concerns—such as privacy risks, group-level harm, or misuse—that were not foreseen at the time of the original collection and fall outside the scope of the original legal or ethical assessment.

Novel ways of combining data or datasets in the context of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL can proceed as long as the data is Anonymised or Pseudonymised and approval has been granted following an Ethics Review, or by a Supervisory Authority or equivalent where required. Where there is doubt that Consent provisions adequately cover the combination of datasets, an Ethics Review should clarify or the opinion of a Supervisory Authority or equivalent should be sought as to whether additional participant Consent is required. This should normally happen within the context of the research project seeking to combine the datasets using the BioData.pt |

ELIXIR PORTUGAL infrastructure and attested through Data Transfer Agreements or similar legal agreements.

Vigilance is expected when the use of data could affect individuals or groups who may be especially **vulnerable** to harm, discrimination, or social disadvantage. This includes, for example, children, individuals with reduced capacity for informed decision-making, and communities that have historically been subject to marginalisation. Any data processing using BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services that may carry a risk of causing harm or perpetuating discrimination should be carefully assessed in advance through appropriate review mechanisms, such as an Ethics Review. Consequently, any data analysis using BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services that may have the potential to cause stigmatisation must be carefully considered and discussed in the context of an Ethics Review in order to obtain further guidance prior to the analyses being undertaken.

In addition to these generally applicable expectations, there are also role-specific responsibilities assigned to Data Providers, Service Providers, and Data Users, each of whom plays a distinct role in ensuring that Personal Data within BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services are handled in accordance with ethical and legal standards.

3. Requirements to be met by Data Providers

Data Providers should ensure that any Personal Data made available through BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services are processed with a valid and clearly identified legal basis, which should be appropriately documented. In order to safeguard participants' privacy, where Consent is relied upon as a legal basis, it should meet applicable legal requirements, including being freely given, specific, informed, and clearly documented.

Personal Data can only be processed if:

- the Data Subject has given their Consent for the purpose of the Processing, or
- the Processing is compliant with an applicable legal authorization,

and the use for biomedical research has been reviewed following an established Ethics Review process.

Drafting Consent forms and obtaining and managing Consent for data collections is entirely the responsibility of the researcher collecting the data deposited in BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services (who may or may not be the same as the Data Provider). The responsibility to ensure that appropriate Consent and/or Ethics Committee or other Supervisory Authority approval is in place before data is deposited and/or made available in the context of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services lies exclusively with the Data Provider. The Data Provider remains responsible for managing the Consent. Consent must be documented. Consent forms should be drafted to adequately cover the use in the context of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services concerning:

- access to and linkage of data that is stored in an electronic database
- sharing of data with other researchers within and outside of the country
- any decisions made regarding the management and communication of findings of individual clinical significance (Incidental Findings), including any obligations data consumers may have to communicate findings, and any pre-set time-limits for the feeding back of results
- the possibility of the data being used in a commercial context

Withdrawal of Consent: Personal Data are to be destroyed upon withdrawal of Consent except in cases where the relevant law allows or requires data retention. The Data Provider is responsible for informing the Service Provider should any such need arise.

Regardless of the legal basis, Data Providers remain responsible for ensuring that the Processing of Personal Data respects the rights and interests of Data Subjects and is accompanied, where appropriate, by an Ethics Review or the implementation of additional safeguards. To ensure fairness and minimise risks of harm, such ethical oversight or additional measures may be particularly relevant in situations where sensitive data, such as genomic or health-related information, are combined with other datasets in ways that could increase the likelihood of re-identification or create new risks to Data Subjects' rights and freedoms.

The Data Provider must ensure that an Ethics Review as required by all relevant law and internationally agreed standards has been completed. An Ethics Review is always

required where the Consent form indicates that Consent has been given on the condition that such review is conducted before data is processed (i.e. used for a given research project). The ethics review must cover the secondary use of data e.g. through submission and managed access through BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services.

Data protection authority approval must be obtained if required by relevant Portuguese or EU law.

Data Providers should also be responsible for determining in advance how potential Incidental Findings will be managed, and for ensuring that any obligations related to Data Subject Consent, and where applicable withdrawal of Consent, are fulfilled before submitting data to BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services.

Where there is a requirement to return Incidental Findings to Data Subjects, the responsibility to ensure that appropriate Consent and mechanisms of feedback, which must have been Consented to by the Data Subject and agreed in an Ethics Review or by a Supervisory Authority, lies exclusively with the Data Provider and must be in place before data is deposited and/or made available in the context of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services.

Even with Consent or a legal basis for Processing Personal Data, the principle of data minimisation has to be taken into account: Data should be de-identified if the research objectives can still be achieved with a de-identified data set.

4. Requirements to be met by Service Providers

Service Providers are responsible for ensuring that appropriate conditions govern access to and use of Personal Data within BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services. This includes the implementation of Terms of Use and, where necessary, additional legal agreements such as Data Processing Agreements (DPAs) or safeguards for international data transfers.

Any Transfer of Personal Data should be based on formal agreements such as Data Transfer Agreements (DTAs) or similar legal instruments. The Service Provider must conclude two types of agreements: one with the Data Provider before data is submitted to the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service and one with the Data User

before data is made available for research. These can be implemented as Terms of Use or Terms of Service.

At the point of data submission ("data in") and where applicable, any such agreement must reflect that the Data Provider is submitting the data to the Service only after having secured the necessary Informed Consent by the Data Subject and/or taking into account any other limitations, such as for example deriving from ethics reviews or relevant law, or the requirement to feedback Incidental Findings. It is advisable that the agreement also include a provision for the Data Provider to inform the Service Provider should the need to remove Personal Data arise for example when Consent is withdrawn.

At the point of data use ("data out"), in the case of data requiring Consent by the Data Subject, it is advisable that the agreement between the Service Provider and the Data User exclude any further data transfer from the side of the Data User or, where such transfer is intended, include a requirement for the Data User to document any such data transfer in case Consent for Personal Data is withdrawn in order to be able to comply commensurately with a revocation of Consent. The Service Provider might also consider referring to the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL ELSI Policy in this agreement. For the avoidance of doubt, the responsibility for meeting any applicable requirements around Consent, Ethics Reviews and Incidental Findings remains with the Data Provider.

Service Providers should ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place to protect the security and confidentiality of Personal Data, including through Access Control mechanisms, and security measures that reflect current best practices.

Physical Security: Adequate measures based on current and continuously updated best practice, which may include formal certification, should be implemented to guarantee the physical security of data during the Processing within the context of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services.

Controlled Access to Data: Controlled access to Personal Data should be implemented unless the available consent or other considerations allow fully unrestricted open access. The Service Provider is responsible for ensuring levels of data security

appropriate for the type of data held. The access procedure should be transparent to ensure fair access. The principles governing the use of data after access has been granted should be outlined in agreements (such as DTAs or Terms of Use). Controlled access to data is provided on the basis of an appropriate data security plan that is based on current and continuously updated best practice and which may include formal certification. Additional restrictions may be imposed by the Service home organisation's IT requirements and policies, e.g. regarding server, network, and application security.

Third Party-Managed IT resources: Increasingly, IT services are moving from local servers and hardware managed by the organisation's own staff to systems owned and managed by third party providers. Transfer and storage of controlled access data on third party systems require additional considerations. Service Providers should ensure that appropriate due diligence and contractual safeguards are in place when using third-party IT resources. Thus, it is advisable that institutions validate that they are partnering with a reputable third party provider and develop appropriate security plans and service agreements before data is migrated to third party providers. Migration of person-related data to servers located in other countries also require consideration of relevant data protection regulation (e.g. in the case of non-EU cloud services, it should be ensured that it is legally allowed, for example because the foreign country has been declared a "safe" country by the EU Commission or the Consent of the Data Subject explicitly allows the transfer).

While the primary responsibility for ensuring that the processing of Personal Data complies with legal and ethical requirements lies with the Data Provider, Service Providers should take reasonable steps, within the scope of their role, to ensure that appropriate access conditions are applied and that any known legal or ethical restrictions accompanying the data are respected and upheld throughout service delivery. The Data Controller overseeing the provision of Personal Data in the context of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services has to ensure that the intended Processing is lawful (e.g. through a Data Access Committee). Where BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services make patient data or data from donors of biomaterial or Genetic

Data available, prime consideration should be given as to whether the Data Provider has given sufficient evidence (e.g. in the context of a DTA or similar agreement) that the available Consent allows this.

5. Requirements to be met by Data Users

Data Users accessing Personal Data through BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services are expected to adhere to the ethical principles set out in this Policy and to comply with all applicable legal agreements governing data access and use, including the Basic Principles concerning Human Dignity and Autonomy, Non-Discrimination, Good Scientific Practice and Public Benefit. Data Users should respect any conditions attached to the use of Personal Data, including restrictions on secondary use, onward transfer, or commercial exploitation. They should ensure that data are not used in ways that could cause harm, discrimination, or distress to individuals or communities, and should seek further ethical advice or review where appropriate.

6. Non-Human Data

All actors involved in BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services—Data Providers, Service Providers, and Data Users—should ensure that the handling of non-human data, including data from plant, microbial, animal, environmental, molecular and cellular sources, is lawful, ethically sound, and aligned with recognised international frameworks.

Ethical concerns related to non-human data include but are not limited to, the obligation to respect the sovereignty, consent, and participation of communities, which includes but is not limited to Indigenous Peoples and those in biodiversity-rich regions, whose environments and knowledge systems are frequently the source of biological materials and data. These concerns may also encompass risks to conservation and ecological balance, the equitable distribution of benefits arising from research, and, in the case of pathogen-related research, potential Dual-Use risks.

6. Requirements to be met by Data Providers

Data Providers should ensure that the acquisition and submission of data is undertaken in a lawful and ethically sound manner, including, where appropriate, the application of prior Consent and benefit-sharing arrangements in line with instruments such as the Nagoya Protocol, the Convention on Biological Diversity, and the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture. Particular care should be taken when data is linked to traditional knowledge or originates from regions with legal protections over biological, including animal, resources.

Where animal data is made available for research via BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services, the Data Provider must ensure that relevant guidelines and laws for the animals' welfare and care during collection of the data are followed, in accordance with the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes.

Where non-human genome data is made available, use and provision in the context of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services must be compliant with the relevant national implementation of the Nagoya Protocol.

Where data may raise Dual-Use concerns—such as pathogen-related or synthetically engineered sequences—Data Providers should assess potential misuse risks, comply with relevant national or international biosecurity and export control laws, and ensure that any restrictions or usage limitations are communicated to Service Providers.

7. Requirements to be met by Service Providers

Service Providers should implement data stewardship practices that are transparent, respectful of access conditions, and responsive to the governance frameworks of contributing countries. Where restrictions on data access or use are imposed by national law or international agreement, Service Providers should ensure these conditions are well-documented, made available to Data Users through metadata or Terms of Use, and technically enforced where feasible through Access Control mechanisms. Services that enable cross-border data sharing should, where appropriate, apply mechanisms that support traceability of data access, enable recording of user

obligations, and facilitate responsible reuse of data in accordance with legal and ethical expectations.

When handling pathogen-related data, particularly in the context of emerging infectious diseases, Service Providers should remain alert to Dual-Use concerns and are encouraged to implement access oversight procedures, consult relevant guidance on data security and ethical use, and liaise with appropriate national or institutional bioethics or biosafety bodies when needed.

These rules can be implemented in Data Transfer Agreements, Terms of Use or Terms of Service, taking the different perspectives described above (Data Provider, Service Provider, Data User) into account.

8. Requirements to be met by Data Users

Data Users are expected to respect any conditions attached to the use of such data, including benefit-sharing expectations, national laws, and the interests of contributing stakeholders.

7. Synthetic Data

Synthetic Data refers to artificially generated datasets that replicate the statistical features of real-world data without directly including information from identifiable individuals. While Synthetic Data offers benefits in promoting data accessibility and protection of privacy, it also presents ethical challenges. These include the residual risk of re-identification, potential propagation of biases from original datasets, and lack of transparency in how the data are generated or validated. To support responsible practice, BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL encourages the documentation of data generation methods, including their intended purpose and limitations, to ensure clarity and promote appropriate use.

9. Requirements to be met by Data Providers

Data Providers contributing Synthetic Data to BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services should ensure that generation methods are appropriately documented and that the resulting datasets respect any original Consent and intended use conditions. Where relevant, risk and bias considerations should be acknowledged.

10. Requirements to be met by Service Providers

Service Providers are encouraged to ensure that synthetic datasets are clearly identified and that accompanying documentation supports transparency regarding their generation and use, and that this information is made available to Data Users.

11. Requirements to be met by Data Users

Data Users are expected to use such data consistently with the principles that form the ethical basis of this Policy and applicable legal requirements.

8. Artificial Intelligence

This section applies to the development, deployment, and use of AI techniques within BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services. This includes services that support AI applications, as well as cases where Data Users apply AI methods—such as algorithms, machine learning models, or large language models (LLMs), where relevant—to data accessed through BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services, or develop AI systems based on such data. The integration of AI systems and techniques within BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services varies depending on the nature of the service. Some services, such as workflow and analysis platforms, increasingly support AI-based pipelines and tools, while others, such as data repositories, primarily enable the storage and sharing of data for potential later AI analysis and use by researchers. Data Providers, Service Providers, and Data Users should ensure that such activities respect fundamental ethical principles, including respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness, and explicability.

The application of AI techniques can introduce risks that vary according to the context and sensitivity of the data involved. Particular care should be taken where AI outputs

could influence scientific conclusions, clinical research, public health, or societal perceptions. In these contexts, all actors should exercise heightened diligence, ensuring that AI use does not inadvertently cause harm, introduce bias, or undermine trust in scientific research.

12. Requirements to be met by Data Providers

Data Providers are advised to ensure that data submissions are complete and accurate and should highlight any known biases, limitations, or uncertainties associated with the data that could influence AI processing or outcomes. While Data Providers may not be able to anticipate or control whether and how AI systems and techniques will be applied to their submitted data, the identification of such factors can support more responsible use by downstream users. If developing AI systems, Data Providers are responsible for complying with ethical and legal standards in accordance with applicable regulations, including the EU AI Act where applicable.

13. Requirements to be met by Service Providers

Service Providers should ensure that, where AI techniques are integrated into services, those services are technically robust, transparent regarding the use of AI, and include mechanisms for human oversight and appropriate evaluation, particularly where AI influences, supports, or automates research processes or decisions.

14. Requirements to be met by Data Users

Data Users are expected to critically assess outputs generated through AI techniques and avoid undue reliance on automated results, especially in contexts where outputs may influence research conclusions, public trust, or affect individuals or groups. Where Data Users develop new AI systems based on data accessed through BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services, they should ensure that such development adheres to applicable legal requirements, including the EU AI Act where applicable, and evolving ethical norms.

Part C - Application

The following section sets out the processes for approving, implementing, and monitoring the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL ELSI Policy to ensure consistent application across all BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services and Node Members.

9. Approval, Implementation and Monitoring of this Policy

15. Approval

The responsibility for the approval of this Policy lies with the **BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Board**.

The BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Head of Node is responsible for ensuring that the Policy is routinely reviewed by the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Scientific Advisory Board in order to improve it and to keep it continuously up-to-date with new advances in basic research and bioinformatics as well as developments concerning ethical and legal requirements.

Feedback from the Heads of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Consortium Members and key expert groups or persons will also be sought regularly.

16. Implementation

Each **BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Node Member** is responsible for ensuring that the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services it provides are aligned with this Policy.

As per Art. 10.1.2g of the Node Collaboration Agreements, the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Head of Node is responsible for ensuring compliance with this Policy for the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services offered by the Node. In turn, Coordinators of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Node Members are responsible for ensuring compliance with this Policy for the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services offered by the respective Node Member.

Node Members are expected to establish internal policies, procedures and legal agreements that support the application of the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL ELSI

Policy in their institutional and operational context. Implementation should reflect both legal obligations—including Portuguese and EU law—and the ethical principles outlined in this document, and respect for fundamental rights.

Compliance with this Policy forms part of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL's shared commitment to responsible data governance across the distributed infrastructure.

17. Monitoring

The Collaboration Oversight Group, which is established by the Parties to the Node Collaboration Agreement and comprises the Head of Node, the Node Coordinator and other individuals appointed by them, shall monitor the compliance of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services provided by the Node Member in question.

In collaboration with the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Scientific Advisory Board and supported by the Node Member in question, data concerning BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service compliance with this Policy will be gathered by the Board of Directors and submitted to the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Scientific Advisory Board in the context of regular BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service reviews.

Upon recommendation of the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Scientific Advisory Board (including Ethics Experts), the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Board shall decide whether it wishes to renew or terminate (in whole or in part) the Agreement with the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Node Member.

18. Information

The BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Head of Node and BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Node Members each play a role in fostering awareness of legal, ethical, and regulatory considerations relevant to the processing of data within BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services. In its coordinating capacity, the Head of Node facilitates knowledge exchange, supports good practice development, and provides guidance on shared challenges, including those related to evolving legal and ethical landscapes. This

role is complementary to the responsibility of individual Node Members to ensure compliance with applicable national and institutional requirements.

The Head of Node of BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL shall remind Node Members of their obligation to ensure compliance with all relevant laws and regulations (and, where applicable, local ethical guidelines) when handling, storing, or processing personally identifiable data resulting from biomedical research.

Glossary of Terms

The definitions below shall be considered only for the purpose of this Policy. Some definitions from the General Data Protection Regulation have been adapted for the purpose of this Policy.

Access Control refers to technical and organisational mechanisms that restrict access to data to authorised individuals under defined conditions.

Anonymous (or Anonymised) Data are data that do not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to data that was personal data at the time they were collected but which, using best practices, have been rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is no longer identifiable.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and may exhibit adaptive behaviour after deployment. AI systems infer, from the data they receive, how to generate outputs—such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions—that can influence physical or virtual environments.

Commissioned Services (CoS) are projects specifically designed and financed in the framework of the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL programme with the purpose to achieve BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL's priorities and ambitions. Each CoS is led and contributed to by one or more Node Members.

Consent means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the Data Subject's wishes by which the Data Subject, either by a statement or by a clear affirmative action (such as a signed document), signifies agreement to Personal Data relating to them being processed.

Data Access Committee (DAC) means a designated group of individuals who are made responsible for reviewing applications and granting permission for access to access-controlled datasets. Decisions to grant access are made based on whether the request conforms to the conditions under which data is made available by the Service. In cases where the DAC considers an Ethics Review necessary but where this is not already available, it can build an ad hoc ethics committee or equivalent body to conduct the appropriate review.

Data Controller (DC) means the natural or legal person who determines (by law or in fact) alone or jointly with others the purposes and means of the Processing of Personal Data.

Data Processing Agreement (DPA) means a legally binding contract between a Data Controller and a Data Processor that governs the processing of personal data on behalf of the Controller.

Data Protection Officer (DPO) means a designated person within an organisation that audits Personal Data; he/she acts independently and is responsible for making sure that the organisation complies with data protection law.

Data Provider means the individual researcher or investigator or group of researchers or investigators, or institution that makes data available or submits data for access and use in the context of a BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service.

Data Subject refers to an identified or identifiable natural person (individual) whose data are accessed (e.g. patients, donors or study participants).

Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) means an agreement or contract made between a Data Provider and a Service Provider (i.e. when data is submitted to a BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service – "data in") or a Service Provider and a Data User (i.e. when a BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service makes data available to researchers – "data out") that governs the conditions under which the data is transferred and defines the rights of the contracting parties regarding future data usage. The DTA can take the form of general terms of service or terms of use.

Data User means the individual researcher or investigator or group of researchers or investigators that accesses and/or uses data made available as part of a BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service.

Dual-Use refers to items, including data, software, or technology, that can be used for both civilian and military purposes. In the context of biological data, it particularly refers to pathogen-related or synthetically engineered sequences that could potentially be misused.

BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service(s) refers to BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Services as defined in the Node Collaboration Agreements, i.e. Node-funded Services or Commissioned Services.

Ethics Review means a process, carried out by an Ethics Committee or other competent body to assess the ethical acceptability of a study or other form of systematic data collection (e.g. biobank). Where required, relevant ethical approvals or other authorisations must be obtained before data is made available through a BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service.

Genetic Data means data relating to the genetic characteristics of an organism that have been inherited or acquired and which may provide unique information about the physiology or the health of that organism or individual.

Incidental Findings are findings concerning an individual discovered in the course of research using data offered in the context of a BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service that are beyond the original aims of the research.

Node-funded Services are services that fall under the administrative and financial responsibility of the Node Member and are part of the Service Delivery Plan.

Personal Data are any information relating to an identifiable natural person (Data Subject); an identifiable natural person is someone who can be identified with reasonable efforts, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, online identifier or one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that person. Genetic Data may be considered non-Personal as long as it does not fulfill the criteria of Personal Data.

Processing means any operation that is performed on Personal Data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available (including use or making available for research purposes), alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

Pseudonymised Data (also known as 'coded' data) are data that can only be connected to the Data Subject by using additional, separately kept information (i.e., a 'key') that would allow certain authorised individuals (e.g. the clinical team who collected the data) to link them back to the identifiable Data Subject.

Sensitive Data means Personal Data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, genetic data, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

Service Delivery Plans outline services that fall under the administrative and financial responsibility of the Node Member (Node-funded Services). Each Node Member, with support from the BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL coordination, will prepare a Service Delivery Plan.

Service Provider refers to the Node Member providing a BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL Service.

Supervisory Authority means an independent public authority established in order to supervise and decide critical issues in a specific area.

Synthetic Data refers to data that is artificially generated—often based on the statistical patterns, structure, and properties of real-world datasets—rather than directly copied or collected from real events or individuals.

Terms of Use refer to terms defining how a BioData.pt | ELIXIR PORTUGAL service may be accessed and used, by whom, and under what conditions, including legal, technical, and policy-related terms applicable to the use of the service.